

IMPORTANCE OF SELF-STUDY IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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Abstract. *the article devoted to the relevance of self-study in education, and learning process for students of higher education as well as individual learners. In fact, self-study benefits not only in the process of learning certain information but also several skills may be enhanced through putting it into use.*

Key words: *self-study, encouragement, techniques, strategies, mindset, flexibility, time management, self-discipline, critical thinking, experience.*

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНЫХ ЗАНЯТИЙ В ИЗУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *Статья посвящена актуальности самостоятельной работы в образовании и учебном процессе для студентов высших учебных заведений, а также индивидуальных обучающихся. Фактически, самообучение приносит пользу не только в процессе изучения определенной информации, но также и в том, что применяя это на практике, можно приобрести необходимые навыки.*

Ключевые слова: *самообучение, поощрение, приемы, стратегии, мышление, гибкость, тайм-менеджмент, самодисциплина, критическое мышление, опыт.*

Self-study has become increasingly important in recent years while learning a foreign language. The beneficial self-studies that are recommended by professors or instructors can help students grow or enhance their language abilities. Students who are learning English as a second language or as a foreign language typically need to be motivated with some exercises and games that encourage positive thinking and creative learning. Students frequently have questions regarding the new terms they learn in introductory English sessions. They also inquire about the many tenses they study each week. To encourage creativity and happiness in their pupils, teachers and instructors employ a variety of techniques and strategies.

Self-study is an important way for individuals to develop and maintain their knowledge and skills. It allows for a level of autonomy and control over one's own learning, which can be empowering and motivating. Additionally, self-study can be tailored to an individual's specific needs, interests, and learning style, making it a more effective way to acquire new information and skills. Moreover, self-study can also be a cost-effective way to learn, as it often does not require the expense of tuition or other fees. Finally, there is a certain set of skills that can be obtained through self-study.

1. Self-study promotes a mindset of lifelong learning. In today's rapidly changing world, knowledge and skills become outdated quickly. Engaging in self-study allows individuals to continuously update their knowledge base, adapt to new technologies, and stay relevant in their fields.

2. Self-study offers flexibility in terms of time and location. Learners can choose when and where they study, allowing them to fit learning into their existing schedules. This flexibility is particularly beneficial for individuals with busy lifestyles, work commitments, or other personal obligations.

3. Self-study enables learners to personalize their learning experience. They can choose the topics, resources, and materials that align with their specific interests and goals. This customization leads to a deeper level of engagement and motivation, as learners are more likely to be invested in subjects they are genuinely interested in.

4. Self-study cultivates self-discipline and time management skills. Since learners are responsible for their own progress and success, they must develop the ability to stay focused, set goals, manage their time effectively, and maintain a consistent study routine. These skills are valuable in various aspects of life beyond education.

5. Self-study promotes independence and empowers individuals to take control of their own learning journeys. It encourages critical thinking, problem-solving, and self-reflection, as learners must actively seek out information, evaluate resources, and assess their own progress. This autonomy fosters a sense of empowerment and self-confidence.

6. Self-study can complement formal education. It allows individuals to delve deeper into subjects of interest, explore additional resources beyond what is covered in formal courses, and broaden their knowledge beyond the curriculum. Self-study can fill gaps in knowledge, reinforce understanding, and enhance overall learning outcomes.

7. Self-study facilitates continuous improvement and personal growth. By regularly engaging in self-study, individuals can identify areas for improvement, set learning goals, and work towards self-improvement. It encourages a growth mindset and the pursuit of excellence.

Overall, self-study is a powerful tool for personal development, skill enhancement, and lifelong learning. It provides individuals with the opportunity to take ownership of their education, adapt to changing circumstances, and thrive in a knowledge-driven world.

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